

International Peer Review Journal

p-ISSN 1817-5562

e-ISSN 1998-037X (Online)

CD-ROM ISSN 1998-0361

The New Iraqi Journal Of Medicine

The Official Journal Of The Iraqi Ministry Of Health

Volume 5 Number 2 August 2009

The New Iraqi Journal of Medicine has agreed the use of the uniform requirements of manuscripts submitted to biomedical journal published by the INTERNATIONAL COMMITTEE OF MEDICAL JOURNAL EDITORS (ICMJE) and it's the first Iraqi peer -review medical journal listed by the ICMJE journal list .The first tow issues of this journal appeared under the title of al Karkh journal of Medicine

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Indexed by Copernicus Index Journal Master List and EMR index medicus

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Hemopoietic and lymphoreticular malignancies in Iraq

Abstract

Background: Hemopoietic and lymphoreticular malignancies comprise mainly leukemia, lymphoma, and multiple myeloma. The annual incidence of non-Hodgkin's lymphomas was reported to be increasing by 3 to 4% in different parts of the developed world during the 1990s, while rates for Hodgkin's disease, myelomas and leukemias were more stable. The aim of this study is to evaluate the pattern of hemopoietic and lymphoreticular malignancies diagnosed by bone marrow examination in the largest series of Iraqi patients with the commoner hemopoietic and lymphoreticular malignancies.

Patients and methods: In the largest series of 63923 Iraqi patients with various types of newly diagnosed cancer registered by the Iraqi Ministry of Health from all Iraqi provinces with the exception of 3 Northern provinces (Sulaimanyia, Erbil, and Dohouk) during five-year period (2000-2004). There were 10330 cases of the commoner hemopoietic and lymphoreticular malignancies (leukemia, lymphoma, and multiple myeloma) accounting for 16% of the total number of Iraqi patients with cancers.

Results: Leukemia was the third most common cancer in Iraq accounting for 7% of all cancers. 4476 cases of leukemia were reported; 2618(58.5%) in males and 1858 (41.5%) in females. 1502 cases of Hodgkin disease were registered

accounting for all cancer cases. 925(61.6%) in males and 577(38.4%) in females. There were 3883 cases of NHL accounting for 6% of all cancers. There were 469 cases of multiple lymphomas accounting for 0.73% of all cancers.

Conclusion: In contrast to many western countries, in Iraq the incidence rate of Leukemias is increasing while trends for the other hematolymphopoietic malignancies are strikingly stable.

Keywords: Hemopoietic, lymphoreticular, malignancies.

Introduction

Hemopoietic and lymphoreticular malignancies are derived from cells of bone marrow and lymphoreticular system comprising mainly leukemia, lymphoma, and multiple myeloma. In addition to the less common conditions such as polycythemia vera, mastocytosis, and malignant histiocytosis. Polycythemia vera is a myeloproliferative, not strictly speaking a neoplastic disorder, but it's commonly included in this category. The incidence of these malignancies is very important because many of them can be cured by modern therapies. The annual incidence of non-Hodgkin's lymphomas was reported to be increasing by 3 to 4% in different parts of the developed world during the 1990s, while the rates of Hodgkin's disease, myelomas and leukemias were more stable. Excesses of non-Hodgkin's lymphomas have been observed in populations exposed to

phenoxy-acetic-acid herbicides, to insecticides and to organic solvents [1, 2].

There is lack of information about the relative prevalence and annual incidence of leukemia, lymphoma, and multiple myeloma in Iraq. The aim of this study is to evaluate the pattern of the commoner forms of hemopoietic and lymphoreticular malignancies diagnosed by bone marrow examination in the largest series of Iraqi patients with these disorders.

Patients and methods

In the largest series of 63923 Iraqi patients with various types of newly diagnosed cancer registered by the Iraqi Ministry of Health from all Iraqi provinces with the exception of 3 Northern provinces (Sulaimanyia, Erbil, and Dohouk) during five-year period (2000-2004). There were 10330 cases of the commoner hemopoietic and lymphoreticular malignancies (leukemia, lymphoma, and multiple myeloma) accounting for 16% of the total number of Iraqi patients with cancers.

Results

Leukemias are heterogeneous malignant neoplasms of leucopoietic cells and are generally classified according to the cell type which predominates.

Leukemias were the third most common cancer in Iraq accounting for 7% of all cancers. 4476 cases of leukemia were reported; 2618(58.5%) in males and 1858 (41.5%) in females. Acute lymphoblastic leukemia was the commonest histopathology accounting for 41.5% of all cases. Acute

myeloid leukemia was the second most common histopathology accounting for 20.5%. Chronic Myeloid leukemia was the third most common histopathology accounting for 11.4%. Table-1 shows the frequency of various leukemias histopathology.

Histopathology	
Acute lymphoblastic	1856(41.5%)
Acute myeloid	917 (20.5%)
Chronic Myeloid	509 (11.4%)
Chronic lymphoid	302
Myeloid	50
Hairy cell	29
Lymphoid	15
Acute monocytic	15
Acute promyelocytic	12
Eosinophilic	3
Erythroleukemia	3
Acute myelomonocytic	2
Mast cell	2
Adult T-cell leukemia/lymphoma	2
Subacute Myeloid	2
Lymphosarcoma cell	2
Basophilic	2

Table (1): The frequency of various leukemias histopathology.

1502 cases of Hodgkin disease were registered accounting for of all cancer cases. 925(61.6%) in males and 577(38.4%) in females .There were 3883 cases of NHL accounting for 6% of all cancers. There were 469 cases of multiple lymphomas accounting for 0.73% of all cancers. Table-1 shows the number of registered cases of the commoner hemopoietic malignancies each year.

Year	Leukemia			Hodgkin's disease			NHL			MM		
	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total
2000	375	304	679	175	118	293	403	270	673	33	31	64
2001	474	316	790	207	118	325	474	316	790	47	29	76
2002	491	301	792	192	140	332	514	315	829	75	59	134
2003	482	341	823	173	119	292	413	265	678	41	38	79
2004	796	596	1392	178	82	260	539	374	913	72	44	116
			4476			1502			3883			469

Table (1): The number of registered cases of the commoner hemopoietic malignancies each year

Discussion

The incidence rate of non-Hodgkin's lymphomas (NHL) is increasing in most Western countries, while trends for the other hematolymphopietic malignancies are strikingly stable. Excesses of non-Hodgkin's Lymphomas have been observed in populations exposed to phenoxy-acetic acid herbicides, to insecticides and to organic solvents. Some of these exposures, in particular TCDD, which is a contaminant of phenoxy herbicides, DDT and chlorinated solvents, have been reported to alter cell-mediated immunity. The incidence of NHL is also increased among subjects with HIV infection and subjects undergoing heart or kidney transplantation, all of whom experience immunodeficiency. A hypothesis that has been put forward recently is that the NHL increase is related to increased exposure to sunlight, which has immunosuppressive effects. From a mechanistic point of view, one can hypothesize that NHL is caused by exposures that induce proliferation and immortalization of B-cells, followed by T-cell impairment entailing cell-mediated immune deficiency [10, 11, 12, 13].

In contrast to many western countries where the incidence rate of non-Hodgkin's lymphomas (NHL) is increasing, while trends for the other hematolymphopietic are strikingly stable, in Iraq the incidence rate of Leukemias is increasing while trends for the other hematolymphopietic malignancies are strikingly stable.

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